

TOP PHARMA INDUSTRY TRENDS TO WATCH FOR IN 2023

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Abstract: The pharmaceutical industry is defined as the discovery, development and production of drugs and medicines. This is widespread, including research, regulation and involvement of chemicals and government agencies. Definition. Pharmaceutical technology is one of the pharmaceutical sciences dealing with the composition, formulation, preparation or manufacturing and quality control of extemporaneously compounded or commercially manufactured drugs.

Keywords: Digital technology, the pharmaceutical industry, pharmaceutical industry of the republic in 2022-2026, Tashkent Pharma Park, immunobiological, radiopharmaceutical and parapharmaceutical preparations.

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Annotatsiya: Farmatsevtika sanoati dori vositalari va dori vositalarini kashf etish, ishlab chiqish va ishlab chiqarish sifatida ta'riflanadi. Bu keng tarqalgan, jumladan, tadqiqot, tartibga solish va kimyoviy moddalar va davlat idoralarini jalb qilish. Ta'rif. Farmatsevtika texnologiyasi - bu eksterna qo'shilgan yoki tijorat maqsadida ishlab chiqarilgan dori vositalarining tarkibi, formulasi, tayyorlash yoki ishlab chiqarish va sifatini nazorat qilish bilan shug'ullanadigan farmatsevtika fanlaridan biri.

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli texnologiya, farmatsevtika sanoati, 2022-2026 yillarda respublika farmatsevtika sanoati, Toshkent farmatsevtika parki, immunobiologik, radiofarmatsevtik va parafarmatsevtik preparatlar.

Абстракт: Фармацевтическая промышленность определяется как открытие, разработка и производство лекарств и лекарств. Это широко распространено, включая исследования, регулирование и участие химических веществ и государственных учреждений. Описание. Фармацевтическая технология — это одна из фармацевтических дисциплин, которая занимается составом, рецептурой, приготовлением или производством и контролем качества лекарственных средств, добавляемых извне или производимых на коммерческой основе.

Ключевые слова: Цифровые технологии, фармацевтическая промышленность, фармацевтическая промышленность республики в 2022-2026 годах, Ташкентский фармацевтический парк, иммунобиологические, радиофармацевтические и парафармацевтические препараты.

EPM conducted a roundtable with several pharma experts to learn what industry trends to watch out for in 2023, from AI drug discovery through to the rise of decentralised trials. “2023 will continue to pave the way for sustainable manufacturing, with many organizations focusing on creating long-term solutions.

Now is the time for new production sites to adopt and introduce new technologies; transforming pharmaceutical manufacturing from being dependent on costly legacy processes. Digital technology speeds up processes by allowing early detection of wear on machine lines. It also helps reduce wastage and recalls by effectively tracking defective batches and enables timely intervention.

Our focus is on creating high-performance and quality manufacturing units that can support smart, connected and intelligent systems. The data is transformed into actionable intelligence by improving several aspects of the supply chain, such as inventory management, trend analysis, forecasting and predictive maintenance of equipment.

The rise of digital health technologies and telemedicine will continue to drive healthcare innovation in 2023. Developments such as medical device integration and software monitoring are focused on home and remote diagnostics, resulting in improved clinical outcomes and pre- and post-consultation counseling. caring for more "educated" patients.

The pharmaceutical industry is at a new stage

The epidemiological situation of the coronavirus infection is still unstable worldwide. The pandemic has been a testing time for the world's pharmaceutical industry, as well as for all industries. The complex epidemiological situation proved once again that the development of the pharmaceutical industry is of strategic importance. Full satisfaction of the population's need for highly effective drugs depends on the level of development of the pharmaceutical industry. Considerable work is being done in this field in our country. The number of enterprises in the system increased sharply as a result of the special attention paid to the pharmaceutical sector in recent years at the initiative of our President. Several regulations have been adopted over the years. As a result of this, it can be noted that during the pandemic, it was possible to provide our people with high-quality and cheap medicines, and the medicines produced in our country were exported to about 20 countries in order to meet the domestic needs. But the scope of our tasks is wide. The population of our country is increasing, and the demand for cheap and modern drugs is increasing year by year. The creation of new privileges and opportunities in the field is an important factor in the quality production of medicines. The decree of the head of our state "On additional measures for the rapid development of the pharmaceutical industry of the republic in 2022-2026" is of great importance as it is aimed at the rapid development of the industry. In particular, it was noted that the provision of high-quality, effective and safe pharmaceutical products to the population, the introduction of advanced scientific and technical achievements and innovations in the pharmaceutical industry, the increase of production in the industry by 3 times, and the level of supply of the domestic market to 80% in natural volume were specially noted. In addition, taking the medicine produced in Uzbekistan to the world market, until January 1, 2025, when exporting pharmaceutical products to all countries, including neighboring countries, up to 50% of the cost of transportation by road and rail, but from 5% of the export value of the products (without transportation costs) (in the case of road transportation) and 7

percent (in the case of rail transportation) providing subsidies for compensation, measures aimed at the development of exports are covered. introduced. What does this give the investor?

In the pharmaceutical industry, there are drugs that are technologically difficult to produce. Their production is not only difficult, but the amount of investment is also high. On the other hand, these types of drugs are mainly drugs purchased by the state. For example, during the pandemic, vaccines are purchased in our country and delivered to the population free of charge. So, the state is the buyer of the entrepreneur. When the entrepreneur produces this type of product, the guarantee given by the state helps to make the investment as intended. If an entrepreneur takes a loan and is unable to sell his product for some reason, it may cause bankruptcy. Therefore, the production of modern anti-oncology or vaccine-type drugs has not been well established in our country for years. Now such a situation is being created that if an investor receives an order for quality, cheap, timely delivery of products based on the requirements, the state, in turn, guarantees the purchase of products from this entrepreneur for 3 years. This will be beneficial for both the state and the entrepreneur.

The industry has had several limitations over the years. For example, in our country, the production of blood preparations, collection of blood from the population, its processing, storage, and the preparation of various medicines from blood plasma were not well established. The reason is that there was a state monopoly. That is, no one but the state, especially the private sector, had the opportunity to collect, store and process blood and produce various types of drugs. However, the need for blood products in our country is increasing. The decree abolished this restriction. That is, the local entrepreneur had the opportunity to produce this type of medicine. Another of the areas that hinders development in the field is the fact that clinical trials do not meet international requirements. Until now, clinical trials in Uzbekistan could only be conducted on patients. It has now been approved for clinical trials on healthy volunteers. In general, the tasks and benefits defined in the document will undoubtedly bring the development of the pharmaceutical industry of our republic to a higher level. At this point, it is appropriate to highlight the following information on the topic. In the Zangiota district of the Tashkent region, an innovative scientific-production pharmaceutical cluster "Tashkent Pharma Park" of great importance in Central Asia is currently being established. This project started two years ago. Nowadays, construction work is accelerated in many objects. In addition to the territory, it is planned to implement a new investment project on the allocated land.

This, in turn, will further expand the possibility of development of our pharmaceutical industry. The legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on drugs and pharmaceutical activity consists of this Law and other legal documents. If the international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulate provisions different from those in this Law, the provisions of the international agreement shall be applied. medicinal products - products created on the basis of one or more medicinal substances (substances) and auxiliary substances of natural and artificial origin, approved for use for disease prevention, diagnosis and treatment. They include immunobiological, radiopharmaceutical and parapharmaceutical preparations, homeopathic, diagnostic and sterilization tools, as well as medicinal substances (substances) intended for the production and preparation of medicinal products;

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